

Optimal moves in tic-tac-toe

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Let S be a nonempty finite set, whose members are called the squares, and \mathcal{W} a set of nonempty subsets of S , called the winning sets. If \mathcal{W} covers S , that is, if each square belongs to some winning set, we say that \mathcal{W} is a hypergraph on S .

Alice and Bob can play the following game, called tic-tac-toe, using a hypergraph \mathcal{W} on S . They play in turn, starting with Alice. Each move consists in occupying an unoccupied square. The game ends when all the squares are occupied. The first player who occupies a full winning set, if such a player exists, wins. Otherwise it is a draw.

One of the main results of the theory is that Bob has no winning strategy, that is, each hypergraph is a victory for Alice or a draw. For a proof see Theorem 1 in

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(The usual tic-tac-toe is a draw.)

Theorem 1. *Let S be a finite set and \mathcal{W} a hypergraph on S . Suppose Alice and Bob have started tic-tac-toe on (S, \mathcal{W}) , that the moves are denoted by $a_1, b_1, a_2, b_2, \dots$, that Bob has just played b_{n-1} , that a_n and a'_n are two unoccupied squares, that the move a_n is optimal, and that we have*

$$a_n \in W \implies a'_n \in W$$

for all winning set W . Then the move a'_n is also optimal. A similar statement applies to Bob.

Let T be a nonempty finite set, whose members are called the squares, let Alice and Bob occupy in turn an unoccupied square, starting with Alice. The process ends when all the squares are occupied.

Let c_1 and c'_1 be two squares. We define the squares

$$d'_1, e_1, d_1, e_2, c_2, f_2, c'_2, f_3, d'_2, e_3, f_4, \dots \tag{1}$$

in the indicated order, as follows:

We set $e_1 = c_1, f_2 = c'_1$, we suppose that

$$c_2, \dots, c_{i-1}, d_1, \dots, d_{i-1}, c'_2, \dots, c'_{i-1}, d'_1, \dots, d'_{i-1}, e_2, \dots, e_{i-1}, f_3, \dots, f_{i-1}$$

have already been defined, we define c_i as an arbitrary square **not** in $\{c_1, d_1, \dots, c_{i-1}, d_{i-1}\}$, we define c'_i and e_i by the rule:

if $c_i \neq f_i$, then $c'_i = c_i$ and $f_{i+1} = f_i$,

if $c_i = f_i$, then $c'_i \notin \{c'_1, d'_1, \dots, c'_{i-1}, d'_{i-1}\}$ with $c'_i = c_1$ if possible, and $f_{i+1} = c'_i$,

we define d'_i as an arbitrary square **not** in $\{c'_1, d'_1, \dots, c'_{i-1}, d'_{i-1}, c'_i\}$, and we define c'_i and e_i by the rule:

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if $d'_i \neq e_i$, then $d_i = d'_i$ and $e_{i+1} = e_i$,

if $d'_i = e_i$, then $d_i \notin \{c_1, d_1, \dots, c_{i-1}, d_{i-1}, c_i\}$ with $d_i = c'_1$ if possible, and $e_i = d'_i$.

The picture below might help the reader:

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc}
 e_1 & & & f_2 & & & f_i \\
 \parallel & & & \parallel? & & & \parallel? \\
 c_1 & d_1 \rightarrow & c_2 & \cdots \rightarrow & c_i & d_i \rightarrow & \cdots \\
 & \uparrow & \downarrow & & \downarrow & \uparrow & \\
 c'_1 \rightarrow & d'_1 & c'_2 \rightarrow & \cdots & c'_i \rightarrow & d'_i & \\
 \parallel & \parallel? & & & \parallel? & & \\
 f_2 & e_1 & & & e_i & &
 \end{array}$$

The horizontal arrows always point to squares which are distinct from the other squares on the same row.

Lemma 2. *The squares on the row $c_1, d_1, c_2, d_2, \dots$ are distinct, and so are the squares on the row $c'_1, d'_1, c'_2, d'_2, \dots$*

Proof. We argue by induction on the cardinality $|T|$ of T . The case $|T| \leq 2$ being obvious, we assume $|T| \geq 3$. Denoting the statement we want to prove by

$$\Sigma(T, c_1, c'_1, d'_1),$$

we see that:

if $d'_1 \neq c_1$, then $\Sigma(T, c_1, c'_1, d'_1)$ is equivalent to $\Sigma(T \setminus \{d'_1\}, c'_1, c_1, c_2)$,

if $d'_1 = c_1$, then $\Sigma(T, c_1, c'_1, d'_1)$ is equivalent to $\Sigma(T \setminus \{c_1\}, c'_1, d_1, c_2)$.

Since $|T \setminus \{a'_{p+1}\}| = |T \setminus \{b_p\}| = |T| - 1$, the proof is complete. \square

Setting

$$C_j := \{c_1, \dots, c_j\}, \quad C'_j := \{c'_1, \dots, c'_j\}, \quad D_j := \{d_1, \dots, d_j\}, \quad D'_j := \{d'_1, \dots, d'_j\},$$

we get

$$c_i \in C'_i, \quad i \geq 2; \quad d'_i \in D_i \sqcup \{c_1\}, \quad i \geq 1,$$

and thus

$$C_j \subset C'_j \cup \{c_1\}, \quad D'_j \subset D_j \sqcup \{c_1\}, \quad j \geq 1. \quad (2)$$

(Here \sqcup means “disjoint union”.) Let $X \subset S$. Assume:

$$c_1 \in X \implies c'_1 \in X. \quad (3)$$

Lemma 3. *We have:*

$$X \subset C_j \implies X \subset C'_j, \quad (4)$$

$$X \subset D'_j \implies X \subset D_j, \quad (5)$$

$$X \cap C_j \neq \emptyset \implies X \cap C'_j \neq \emptyset, \quad (6)$$

$$X \cap D'_j \neq \emptyset \implies X \cap D_j \neq \emptyset. \quad (7)$$

Proof of (4). We have $X \subset C_j \subset C'_j \cup \{c_1\}$ by (2). We can assume $c_1 \in X \setminus C'_j$, and it suffices to derive a contradiction. We get $c'_1 \in X \subset C_j$ by (3), and thus

$$c_1 \in C_j \setminus C'_j, \quad c'_1 \in C_j \cap C'_j. \quad (8)$$

Since $c'_1 \in C_j$, there is a k such that $2 \leq k \leq j$ and

$$c'_1 = c_k. \quad (9)$$

We have $c'_k = c_1$ if possible. But $c'_k \neq c_1$ because $c_1 \notin C'_j$ by (8). Hence there is an m with $2 \leq m \leq k - 1$ and $(c'_m = c_1 \text{ or } d'_m = c_1)$. But $c'_m \neq c_1$ again because $c_1 \notin C'_j$ by (8). Hence $d'_m = c_1$. Then $d_m = c'_1$ if possible. But (9) implies that Equality $d_m = c'_1$ is possible, and that it leads to a contradiction. \square

Proof of (5). Assume $X \subset D'_j$. Then $X \subset D'_j \subset D_j \sqcup \{c_1\}$ by (2). Let $x \in X$. It is enough to show $x \neq c_1$. Assume by contradiction $x = c_1$. Then (3) implies $c'_1 \in X \subset D'_j$, contradiction. \square

Proof of (6). Let $x \in X \cap C_j$. Then $x = c_k$ with $1 \leq k \leq j$, hence $c_k \in C_j \subset C'_j \cup \{c_1\}$ by (2).

If $k = 1$, then $c'_1 \in X$ by (3), hence $c'_1 \in X \cap C'_j$.

If $k \neq 1$ then $c_k \neq c_1$, hence $c_k \in X \cap C'_j$. \square

Proof of (7). Assume $X \cap D'_j \neq \emptyset$. Let $d'_k \in X$ with $1 \leq k \leq j$. Then $d'_k \in D'_j \subset D_j \sqcup \{c_1\}$. We can assume

$$d'_k = c_1 \in X. \quad (10)$$

Then $c'_1 \in X$ by (3), and $d_k = c'_1$ if possible. We claim:

$$\text{Equality } d_k = c'_1 \text{ is possible.} \quad (11)$$

This will imply $d_k = c'_1 \in X \cap D_j$, and prove (7). Assume by contradiction that $d_k = c'_1$ is impossible. Then there is an m with $1 \leq m \leq k$ and $c_m = c'_1$, or there is an m with $1 \leq m \leq k - 1$ and $d_m = c'_1$.

In the first case we have $c'_m = c_1$ if possible. But (10) implies that $c'_m = c_1$ is possible, and that it leads to a contradiction.

In the second case we have $d'_m = d_m$ (because $d'_m \neq d'_k = c_1$ by (10)), hence $d'_m = d_m = c'_1$, contradiction.

This proves (11), and thus (7). The proof of Lemma 2 is complete. \square

Proof of Theorem 1. Set $c_1 = a_n, c'_1 = a'_n$; define the squares $d'_1, e_1, d_1, e_2, c_2, f_2, c'_2, f_3, d'_2, e_3, f_4, \dots$ as explained after (1); and for $i \geq n$ set

$$a_i = c_{i-n+1}, \quad b_i = d_{i-n+1}, \quad a'_i = c'_{i-n+1}, \quad b'_i = d'_{i-n+1}.$$

Note that the c_i and the d'_i were defined as arbitrary unoccupied squares. But now we redefine the $c_i = a_{i+n-1}$ as the moves given by Alice's strategy. (The $d'_i = b'_{i+n-1}$ remain arbitrary unoccupied squares.) Note that T is given by $T = S \setminus \{a_1, b_1, a_2, b_2, \dots, a_{n-1}, b_{n-1}\}$, that the subset X in Lemma 3 is given by $X = W \cap T$, where W is a winning set, and that Condition (3) follows from our assumptions on a_n and a'_n . Then the lemmas furnish the desired conclusion. \square